

IMPACT OF ROLE SPILLOVER ON EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION IN SELECTED PUBLIC TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The focus of this research is to unveil the dynamic relationship between role spillover and job satisfaction of workers in chosen public higher educational institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The study was survey and questionnaire was administered to 380 respondents out of a population of 7, 416 workers which was determined through Taro Yamane formula. This was followed by data analyses using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The findings showed that work-family enrichment ($\beta = 0.930, t = 13.549, P = 0.000$) and work-family balance ($\beta = 0.196, t = 4.593, P = 0.000$) positively and significantly enhance employee job satisfaction, while work-family conflict ($\beta = -181, t = -3.349, P = 0.001$) negatively and significantly influences job satisfaction in the affected establishments. It was concluded that job facilitation will enhance work-family balance and reduce work-family conflict thereby improving job satisfaction among staff.

Keywords: Role Spillover, Work-Life Enrichment, Work-Life Balance, Work-Family Conflict, Employee Job Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, role spillover has become increasingly prevalent in modern-day work-life interfaces (Luan, et al, 2022), especially in Nigerian tertiary institutions. This is because employees' wellbeing extends from one domain of life to another. As employees navigate from one domain to another, emotions, moods, and feelings are transferred, thereby impacting on their performances and their levels of satisfaction with the job (Ilies, et al, 2009). Role spillover is a boundary management strategy representing a cross-domain influence of an employee's emotional, mental, or physical state, impacting on their overall quality of life (Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016).

Role spillover can be positive or negative (Verfuert & Gregaory-Smith, 2018). Positive role spillover describes the synergistic effect where a positive construct (e.g., job satisfaction) in one domain enhances a related construct (e.g., life satisfaction) in another domain (Chakrabarti, 2011). Conversely, negative role spillover occurs when employees encounters work-family conflict which results to a sacrifice of leisure due to workload in office (Lakshmypriya et al. 2016).

Employees' experiences at work and home are intertwined, with stress and unpleasantness in one area potentially influencing behaviours and attitudes in the other (Amstad et al., 2011).

The negative consequences of boundary integration otherwise known as role blurring has been the major concern of role spillover (Lee, et al, 2021). But due to the importance of work-life facilitation or work-life enrichment, research interest on the topic has risen (Mudion, et al, (2021). Although two domains exists in boundary management- work and personal or family life and to navigate between the two, an individual's commitment in one (e.g. work) through experience may improve his or her engagement in the other (personal or family life).

The extent to which an individual employee's engagement in a particular domain influences his or her engagement in the other is referred to as work-life enrichment (Maertz & Boyar, 2011). In the opinion of Frone (2000), work-life enrichment occurs when workers gather experiences, skills or competencies in one role domain which enhances their effectiveness in the other role domain.

Work-life enrichment as it relates to boundary management tactics has been proven to enhance job satisfaction, work-life balance and effectiveness of workers (Carlson et al., 2011). This beneficial knock-on impact has important ramifications for companies looking to increase quality of life and efficiency (Allen et al., 2014).

Employee wellbeing is deeply tied to role blurring or integration, but when work takes precedence, it can lead to resource drain and imbalance, leading to work-life conflict (Nwafili, et. al, 2024). It is however imperative for a worker to strike a balance between work obligations and personal life (Arif & Farooqi, 2014).

Work-life balance entails proper handling of work and family obligations such that none lags behind the other (Popoola & Fagbola, 2023). Employees' wellbeing is significantly impacted by work- life balance (Bocean et al., 2023). In particular, the job satisfaction of lecturers in higher institutions are influenced by work-life balance (Arif & Farooqi, 2014).

However, higher-level institutional employees often face role conflicts due to conflicting demands from multiple domains (Sampson, 2011). Focusing on one role can hinder fulfilling obligations in another, leading to clashes (Nwafili, 2024). Role conflict, or role incompatibility, arises from factors like work overload, job stress, occupational burnout, and poor health (Tuffour & Bortey, 2022).

Employees' professional and personal life imbalance exacerbates this challenge, resulting in role conflict (Priyanka et al., 2022). Consequently, role conflict adversely affects employee job satisfaction, undermining overall wellbeing and productivity (Su & Jiang, 2023).

Meanwhile, job satisfaction is essential for inspiring workers, improving output, and guaranteeing retention in organizations (Ajufoh et al., 2024). The concept is perceived as a sense of fulfilment and pleasure in one's workplace (Alig, 2023). In fact, it includes how content and healthy workers are in their workplace (Nwafili et al., 2024). It is commonly acknowledged that employee performance and productivity are significantly influenced by job satisfaction (Dziuba et al., 2020).

Workplace culture, pay and benefits, opportunities for professional development, and management leadership style are the four main aspects that can affect it (Wang, 2024).

Job satisfaction is a complex phenomenon involving a confluence of psychological, physiological, and environmental factors that promote a positive work experience (Aziri, 2011). Role spillover effects on work satisfaction is bidirectional: positive spillover boosts satisfaction, while negative spillover undermines it (Ilies et al., 2009).

Despite the importance of spillover on workers efficiency and effectiveness, employees at various tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria encounters numerous challenges owing to spillover. This has resulted in emotional weariness, diminished motivation and a lower job satisfaction (Amstad et al., 2011).

Although, there have been many study on role spillover and work satisfaction, still a substantial knowledge vacuum regarding Nigerian higher education, especially in Delta State exists. This study intends to fill the knowledge vacuum.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES FORMULATION

2.1 Theoretical Review – Spillover Theory

The spillover theory, a popular framework in work-life interface, postulates that substantial relationships exist between the two interconnected entities, such that there is a crossover effects between the domains (Kumar & Janakiran, 2017). Role spillover assumes that emotions, tension, and ideas that originated from one responsibility are carried over to another. (Sampson, 2011).

According to research, role spillover occurs when there is boundary integration or boundaryless domains, causing similarities and interactions between the two obligations (Ilies et al., 2009). Spillover refers to the potential of an employee's level of wellbeing to be transferred from one domain to another (Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016).

Research has demonstrated that employees' emotions, sentiments, attitudes, abilities, and actions spread across many domains (Kumar & Janakiram, 2017, Ilies et al., 2009, Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016). Spillover is bidirectional (Sampson, 2011), it flows to either side of the domains manifesting as affective or behavioral (Ilies et al., 2009).

Research by Chakrabarti (2011) revealed that emotional states (affect), core values, skill sets, and observable behaviors are the key drivers of similarity between work and home environments. The way and manner by which employees carry over moods or attitudes bidirectionally is called role spillover.

Affect encompasses both mood and attitude, but whereas attitude tends to be more of a relatively stable trait, mood is more transient and prone to fluctuation (Carlson, et al, 2011, Ilies et al., 2009).

2.2. Hypothesis Formulation

2.2.1. Employees Job Satisfaction (EJS)

Employee job satisfaction describes employee favourable emotions and attitudes an employee holds regarding their employment experience within an organization (Buba et al., 2024). It is the extent to which workers are happy, contented, and fulfilled with their work duties and organizational culture (Nwafili et. al., 2024). Job satisfaction, according to Priyanka et al. (2022), is a favourable emotional reaction a person has when assessing their employment or work experiences. According to Tuffour and Bartey (2022), it is a person's general attitude and emotional condition about his or her employment and work surroundings. This implies that the condition of service and work environment are determining factors.

2.2.1. Work – Life Enrichment (WLE) and Employees' Job Satisfaction

This is also known as positive spillover, and it is strengthened by autonomy in the workplace and supportive relationships, ultimately enhancing job performance and overall well-being (Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016). It is seen as work-family facilitation (Lourel, et al, 2009; Frone, 2000) and it refers to the mutually beneficial situation whereby resources, abilities, and experiences acquired in role responsibility (work or family) make duties in the other easier and better (Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016).

Work-family facilitation represents the magnitude of opportunities, experiences, and abilities gained from a particular responsibility, thereby making participation in the other easier and more convenient (Frone, 2000). In the opinion of Chakrabarti (2011), positive work-family spillover is where a construct in one domain is positively related to another different but similar construct in another domain. The idea is mutually beneficial influence of both domains (Lourel et al., 2009).

As stated by Ilies et al. (2009), work-family facilitation results from a situation where attitudes or moods associated to work are carried over to the home or vice versa. Despite having similar affective qualities, mood and attitude are not the same in terms of consistency and goal. While attitude is more steady and purposeful, mood fluctuates rapidly and lacks a clear goal (Lourel et al., 2009).

However, segmentation hinders work-life facilitation (Kossek et al., 2012) and affective work-family enrichment (Allen et al., 2014). When behaviors and abilities from one domain affect the achievement of goals in another, this is known as instrumental spillover (Henn et al., 2020). In value based spillover, value gained in one areas enables better role implementations in other areas (Elf et al., 2019).

Employees' effectiveness and work-life balance as well as job satisfaction are impacted by work-life enrichment (Brough, et al., 2014). This assertion relied on theories of accumulation and conservation of resources (Carlson et al. 2011), both theories assumed that employees' resources, such as energy, time, skills, etc., can neither be fixed nor subject to depletion alone but rather expanded or increased through investment in the resources of one role domain, which will eventually results in a reciprocal increase in the resources of another role domain. Sampson

(2011) argued that positive work-family spillover is significantly correlated with life quality indicators. Workers who are happier at work are more likely to have positive affect at home (Ilies et al., 2009).

Furthermore, Luan, Lv, and Wang (2022) believed that organizational citizenship conduct has a positive correlation with employee job satisfaction and that employee life satisfaction indirectly influences customer satisfaction through service-oriented organizational citizenship behaviour (Mohammad et al., 2011).

H₁: Work-life enrichment impacts positively and significantly on employee job satisfaction.

2.2.2. Work- Life Balance (WLB) and Employees' Job Satisfaction.

In today's contemporary society, work-life balance has gained attention since most employees focus the most of their time, energy, and efforts on their jobs without making the same commitments in their personal and family lives. This causes tension for the employees, which makes them unhappy (Nwafili et al., 2024). To prevent imbalance and role conflict, employees must now balance their job and family obligations (Arif & Farooqi, 2014).

Work-life balance involves striking a balance between personal activities, family life, and employment for the maintenance of their general wellbeing (Susanto et al., 2022). It entails a conscious commitment to promoting employees' well-being, productivity, and personal fulfilment in a variety of spheres of life (Bocean et al., 2023).

According to Liu, et al., (2019) work-family balance necessitates two perceptions; - little interference between work and family (low conflict) and substantial positive spillover (high enrichment). It entails allocating time and energy to address both demands while effectively balancing work and family obligations (Popoola & Fagbola, 2023).

Employees' work-life balance and job satisfaction can be achieved by adopting a positive boundary management technique (Nwafili, 2024). The aim of balancing both roles by employees is to enhance corporate productivity, society prosperity, and personal well-being (Shaikh et al., 2023). Various empirical literatures revealed a positive significant relationship between employees' work-life balance and job satisfaction of workers (Bocean, et al, 2023, Buba, et al, 2024, Arif & Farooqi, 2014).

H₂: Work-life balance impacts positively and significantly on employee job satisfaction

2.2.3. Work-Family Conflict (WFC) and Employees' Job Satisfaction

Work-life conflict results from role incapability. It is defined as the inability of employees to efficiently fulfil professional and personal obligations Nwafili (2024). In such situation, more attention, resources, and time are given to one role domain at the expense of the other, leading to resource drain (Nwafili et al., 2024).

Role conflict results from clashes between job responsibilities and family responsibilities, thereby impeding the fulfilment of one responsibility in one domain due to the participation in the other domain (Linh, et al, 2016). It occurs when work commitments clash with home duties, such as when long workdays make it difficult to do household chores (Priyanka et. al., 2022).

The result of role conflict are decreased organizational commitment, job performance, work-burnout, work stress, and ill health (Amstad et al., 2011). Derks in Nwafili (2024) posits that role conflict is bidirectional; a situation whereby commitments at work conflict with those at home, and vice versa. Role conflict arises from employees' incapacity to manage their job and family responsibilities (Tuffour & Bortey, 2022).

Organizations suffer greatly from work-family conflict, which lowers employee satisfaction (Maerts & Boyar, 2011). Compared to doctors and engineers, university professors suffer dissatisfaction due to role conflict (Priyanka et al., 2022). Employees' inability to integrate both professional and personal roles suffer job dissatisfaction (Tuffour & Bortey, 2022). Hence, role conflict has negative significant impact on employees' job satisfaction (Su & Jiang, 2023).

H₃: Work-life conflict impacts positively and significantly on employee job satisfaction.

2.2.3. Conceptual Framework of Variables

Figure 1: Researchers' Model

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sampling Techniques and Data Collection

This study adopted survey research design method. This is because of its ability to successfully find patterns, connections, and links, as was noted by Kumar (2019). Six higher institutions in

Delta state were purposely chosen for this study and the establishments selected cut across the three senatorial districts of the state.

The study population consisted of 7,416 workers, made up of both academic and non- academic staff. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula stated below;

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \\
 n &= \frac{7,416}{1 + 7,416(0.05)^2} \\
 n &= \frac{7,416}{1 + 7,416(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{7,416}{1 + 18.54} \\
 &= \frac{7,416}{19.54} \\
 &= 379.5
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the sample size is **380**.

Note; n = Size of the sample, N= Study population and e= Level of Significance (5%).

The instrument utilized for collecting primary data was structured questionnaire which was divided into two parts made up of part 1 which was concerned with respondents’ bio-data and part 2 which focuses on questions relating to research hypotheses.

The questionnaire was structured in 5 points likert scale; ranging from ‘strongly agree’ to ‘strongly disagree’. To guarantee representative participation, the study used stratified random sampling. Individual staff members were then chosen using simple random sampling. This methodology ensured equal chances of selection for all employees.

Proportional stratification was used to determine the number of questionnaire to be administered in each establishment and this was calculated based on its proportion to the total population (Nwafili, 2024).

The formula is given as follows:

$$n_i = (N_i/N) \times n$$

Table 1: Proportional Stratification of the Sample Size

S/N	Names of Universities in South-South Nigeria	population	Sample Size $n_i = (N_i/N) \times n$
1.	Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State.	2,800	$2,800/7,416 \times 380 = 143$
2.	Nigeria Maritime University, Okerenkoko, Delta State	1,300	$1,300/7,416 \times 380 = 67$
3.	Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State	723	$723/7,416 \times 380 = 37$
4.	Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro, Delta State.	423	$423/7,416 \times 380 = 22$
5.	Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwashi-Uku, Delta State.	700	$700/7,416 \times 380 = 36$
6.	Federal College of Education Technical, Asaba, Delta State.	1,470	$1,470/7,416 \times 380 = 75$
	Total	7,416	380

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

3.2. Validity and Reliability of Measuring Instruments

Expert evaluation was used to guarantee the validity of the research tool. However, the reliability of the measuring instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient with the aid of pilot study. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.60 or more is regarded as dependable by the researcher, and all constructs were found to surpass this threshold.

3.3. Model Specification and Estimation Strategy

The impact of role spillover (an independent variable) on employee work satisfaction (a dependent variable) was investigated. Employees' job satisfaction (EJS) is a function of Role Spillover (RSO) and Role Spillover (RSO) is measured by Work-Life Enrichment (WLE), Work-Life Balance (WLB), and Work-Family Conflict (WFC). On the other hand, Employee Job Satisfaction is measured by; measured by Employees' Loyalty, Employees' Commitment and Employees' Sense of Ownership. Therefore, the study's model is specified below;

$$EJS = f(RSO) \text{-----(1)}$$

$$EJS = f(WLE, WLB, WFC) \text{----- (2)}$$

$$EJS = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_n) \text{----- (3)}$$

The multiple variate equation model is;

$$EJS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_n X_n + \mu \text{..... (4)}$$

Data was analyzed descriptively and inferentially. The research question was tested with descriptive statistics such as mean deviation while the research hypothesis was tested using multiple regression.

4.0. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

We distributed a total of 380 questionnaires, and a 75% response rate resulted in 285 completed and useable responses.

Table 2: Administration of Questionnaire

Pattern Focused	Number of Questionnaire Administered	Number of Questionnaire Returned	Number of Questionnaire properly filled and Used	Number of Questionnaire not properly filled	Percentage of Questionnaire Used
Higher institution's employees	380	290	285	5	75%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.1. Socio-Economic Features of the Respondents

The analysis of the biographic data are presented in the table below, highlighting factors that impact role spillover and employees' job satisfaction.

Table 3: Biographic Profile of the Respondents

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
Gender	285	1	2	1.44	.029	.497	.247
Age	285	1	5	2.80	.073	1.236	1.529
Marital Status	285	1	2	1.63	.029	.483	.234
Number of Children	285	1	6	2.66	.087	1.471	2.163
Type of Employee	285	1	2	1.32	.028	.466	.217
Work Hours /Day	285	1	2	1.30	.027	.458	.210
Valid N (listwise)	285						

Source: SPSS Output

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

4.2.1. Analysis of Responses

Decision rule: Accept any mean greater than or equal to 3.0 and reject any mean less than 3.0.

Table 4: What is the effect of work-family enrichment on employee job satisfaction?

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Means	Remarks
1.	My work engagement equips me with skills to handle my family roles	67	68	80	40	30	3.358	Accept
2.	My job enables me gain knowledge to become a better family person.	55	58	70	50	52	3.049	Accept
3.	My work always puts me in a good mood thereby enhancing the performance of my personal life roles.	39	45	95	56	50	2.884	Reject
4.	My family involvement puts me on a happy mood thereby enhancing my work performance.	62	68	65	49	41	3.214	Accept
5.	Family involvement taught me time management which makes me a better staff.	60	62	61	52	50	3.105	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2024

A study on tertiary institution employees revealed that job facilitation impacts positively on job satisfaction. Specifically, work enrichment enhances family relationships (means = 3.358, 3.049) and family involvement increases happiness, leading to better work performance (mean = 3.214).

However, work involvement doesn't significantly impact mood (mean = 2.884), and employees' family roles promote productivity and efficient time management (mean = 3.105).

Research Question 2

Table 5: How does work-life balance affect employees' job satisfaction?

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Means	Remarks
6	I've got sufficient time to spend on myself and with friends.	46	38	89	62	50	2.888	Reject
7	I've got sufficient time to carry out my personal activities.	50	40	84	59	52	2.919	Reject
8	I've got sufficient time to satisfy my personal interest.	42	47	55	72	69	2.723	Reject
9	I detach immediately from work once I am out of office.	49	52	50	64	70	2.811	Reject
10.	I worked on challenging time during my free time	61	78	59	46	41	3.253	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2024

Employees reported struggling with work-life balance, thereby impacting job satisfaction. The survey revealed: insufficient personal time (mean = 2.888) and time for friends, inadequate time for personal matters (mean = 2.919), limited pursuit of personal interests (mean = 2.723), persistent work-related thoughts beyond work hours (mean = 2.811), and tendency to work during spare time (mean = 3.253).

Research Question 3

Table 6: In what ways do work-family conflict affect employee job satisfaction?

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Means	Remarks
11.	I usually exceed my work schedule in office	70	65	43	48	59	3.137	Accept
12.	My work is becoming harder now than before.	62	68	59	50	46	3.175	Accept
13.	My HOD reaches out to me for work-related matters in my off days.	60	62	35	67	61	2.975	Reject
14.	I frequently give up sleep to get to fulfil my work responsibility	69	74	56	48	38	3.309	Accept
15.	I experienced more pressure/stress on me at work	58	69	63	42	53	3.130	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2024

Role conflict impacts on employee job satisfaction with employees: working extended hours (mean=3.137), experiencing increased workload difficulty (mean=3.137), sacrificing sleep (mean=3.309), and feeling heightened pressure (mean=3.130). Yet, they resist work-related contacts during spare time (mean = 2.975).

Question 4

Table 7: Question on Employees Job Satisfaction

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Means	Remarks
16.	My job is like a hobby to me	76	62	54	45	48	3.256	Accept
17.	Work is never boring in my establishment.	59	70	81	39	36	3.270	Accept
18.	I am happier than average employee in my office	49	62	101	42	31	3.196	Accept
19.	My job satisfaction is higher than other employees.	57	47	120	37	24	3.267	Accept
20.	Genuine pleasure is found in my job	38	46	106	50	45	2.937	Reject

Source: Field survey, 2024

Regarding job satisfaction, employees reported a positive outlook. They found their jobs engaging, akin to a hobby (mean = 3.256), and stimulating enough to prevent boredom (mean = 3.270). Additionally, they expressed greater happiness and job satisfaction compared to average workers. However, they did not fully agree that their jobs bring them genuine enjoyment.

4.3. Test of Hypotheses

Table 8: Multiple Regression Table

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.398	.135		10.354	.000
	Work-Life Enrichment	.930	.069	.986	13.549	.000
	Work-Life Balance	.196	.043	.212	4.593	.000
	Work-Family Conflict	-.181	.054	-.205	-3.349	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Job Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Output

Hypothesis one result reveals a significant positive relationship between WLE and EJS ($\beta = 0.93, t = 13.549, P = 0.000$). Based on this result, the alternative hypothesis which states that WLE impacts significantly and favourably on EJS is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Likewise, hypothesis two result revealed a significant relationship between the WLB and EJS in the concerned higher institutions ($\beta = 0.196, t = 4.593, P = 0.000$). The alternative hypothesis, which asserts a positive correlation between WLB and EJS, is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected

Hypothesis three result unveiled a significant and negative relationship between WFC and EJS ($\beta = -.181$, $t = -3.349$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$). This result illustrates the detrimental effect of WFC on EJS, hence support the rejection of the alternative hypothesis and the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that WFC impacts negatively on EJS.

4.3. Discussion of Findings

With a beta coefficient (β) of 0.930, the result of data analysis of hypothesis one indicates an existence of favourable and significant relationship between WLE and EJS. This suggests that shifts in WLE account for 9.3% of the variation in employee job satisfaction. By implication, there will be a 9.3% rise in EJS for every upward shifts in WLE.

Conversely, a downward shift in WLE will result in 9.30% fall in EJS. This relationship is too significant to overlook as it is capable of affecting employees and organization performances. However, it was revealed that work engagement helps employees become better family members, gain useful knowledge and put them in good mood.

Likewise, family involvement makes employees happy in work place and equally taught them time management. The current study agrees with Carlson et al. (2011) which posits a favourable and significant relationship exists between WFE and EJS

However, hypothesis two regression analysis result shows that WLB impacts favourably and significantly on EJS ($\beta = 0.196$, $t = 4.593$, $p = 0.000$). According to this result, there is a 1.96% difference in EJS for every unit change in WLB. EJS increases as WLB increases in the affected higher institutions and vice versa.

Factors that enhance WLB are having time for friends, personal matters, leisure, psychological detachment, and work-family. This study demonstrates that WLB has a favourable and statistically significant impact on employee job satisfaction, which is in line with the findings of Bocean et al. (2023) and Buba et al. (2024).

The regression result of hypothesis three revealed an unfavourable and significant impact of WFC on EJS ($\beta = -0.181$, $t = -3.349$, $p = 0.001$), implying that EJS is negatively impacted by WFC. This suggests that a change in the unit of WFC will result in a 1.81% in EJS. It is implied that WFC and EJS are inversely correlated, a situation whereby WFC results to lower EJS and a decrease in WFC will result to better EJS.

Factors influencing WFC include; work duty encroaching on the time for family duty, work becoming more tedious, supervisors/boss' interference with employees' spare time over work related issues, employees' sacrifice of sleep to fulfil work duties and increased work pressure/stress.

The current study's results align with Su and Jiang (2023), who revealed that employees experiencing difficulties in balancing work and family obligations frequently report dissatisfaction with their job roles.

5.0. SUMMARY

5.1. Theoretical and Managerial Implications

Theoretical Implications: This study enhances the knowledge of role spillover theory by demonstrating the significance of WFE, WLB and WFC in shaping employee outcomes. The study confirms that autonomy and supportive relationships at work enable positive spillover, leading to improved performance and well-being, whereas role conflicts result in job dissatisfaction (Lakshmypriya & Krishna, 2016).

Managerial Implications: Research indicates that work-family enrichment, or positive role spillover, enhances autonomy by facilitating flexibility in work schedule, supportive conditions, and policies that foster WLB, ultimately mitigating WFC.

Therefore, school authorities are encouraged to allocate resources to support employees' WLB and role spillover and provide training involving time management and boundary management to encourage employees' work-life interface and employee engagement to improve employee job satisfaction.

6.0. CONCLUSION

This study investigated role spillover and its impact on employee job satisfaction in chosen government owned higher education organizations in Delta State, Nigeria. The findings provide compelling evidence that role spillover, comprising WLE, WLB and WLC, significantly influences employee job satisfaction. This study demonstrates that cultivating WLE and WLB will yield favourable benefits on EJS, while mitigating WFC is crucial to prevent its detrimental effects.

Limitations

Although this research contributes to the existing literature, its limitations highlight areas for future exploration. The study's focus on six public tertiary institutions in Delta State was balanced by representative sampling. Future research should investigate role spillover in various industries to elucidate its far-reaching implications.

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